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PhD research on Economic Growth and Development and Its Dependence on Operations Management Practices

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Abstract

The dream of economic Development and growth is only possible with the economic development.with out the economic development the dream of prosperus is only possible with economics growth and development.Industrial Development is the importance part of the economic growth.Indusrtial growth is only possible with supply chain management.operation management is the integreal part of industrial development.operation management boost the economic growth land industrial Development.operation management provide the way how to utilization of fector of production.with the help of operation management you can achieve the optimum level of fector of production.Material management is the important part of operation management.Material management play the dynamic role in the economic growth.If we maintain the better material management we can achieve the target of production.In the material management different model applied for the requirements of material,with the help of these model we can estimate about the requirement of material.proculment and purchase is the importance part of operation management.with the help of procurement we can batter acquire the resource according to the need of business.in procurement the difference stander are applied for the purchase of goods.cost volume anylasis is the important part of operation management,in this anylization the cost is minimize regarding the acquire of resources.Quality control is the important part of operation management.with the help of quality control management how we attain the better stander of production.Quslity control management provide the principles how to attain the stander of goods.[1],[2],[3],[4],[6],[[7],[8],[11]

Keywords: *Economics, growth , development, operation management.*

Literature review

Operation management is the important way and subject in this era of globalization,with out operation management the concept of accuracy is not possible.The actual meaning of operation management the supply of material should reach to actual customer.operation management is possible only with the help of estimation of material needs and requirement.In the concept of operation management we estimate the economic order quantity,with the help of economic order quantity we can estimate the material requirements for the production proces.quantity.The basic purpose of operation management is to maintain the quantity of material in the different situation.We can estimate how the material is needed in the different situations.operation m management give lesson how the material can reach the actual place.The basic fector in the operation management that the material should reach in the reasonable time.In such cases when the material reach in the reasonable time the operation management will be the successfull.operation management is very important in the production management. Production can be successfully with the help of operation management.

[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[11].

Japan Is The Example Of Economic Growth With Operation Management.

In the Japan the operation management is very successfully because of disaster management. Disaster management can be possible with the help of supply chain and operation management .Many software are introduced,some for the success of supply chain management .Many application software are available for the implantation of supply chain management,material management,with the help of applications they can all the functions of operation management properly.[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[11].

Education of Operation Management Link with Economic Growth.

operation management is very important for such business professional who are involve in the construction business,with the help of operation management we can increase the efficiency of the business activity which is relate to the operation and production management.As far as the qualifications stance is concerned of operation and supply chain managemen,many professional institute provide the qualification of operation and supply chain management,for example institute of supply chain give the opportunity of professional education regarding the supply chain management and operation management. Operation management and Supply chain management subjects are included in the syllabus of business management qualifications like MBA.BBA.Engeering and other stream of the Business management courses.It is the need of hour that we should promote the education of operation and supply chain management. Operation and Supply chain provide the way of Development.With the help of operation management we can increase the efficiency of business activity in every sector.[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9].

Operation Management and Economic Growth.

Operation management play the dynamic role in the country economy.with the help of good operation management we can increase the gross domestic product.production management is the important part of operation management.with the help of operation management we can utilize our Fectors of production like Land,capital,machine, organization.material management is the important part of production,if the material provided at the right place and in the right time it will increase help to increase the industrial growth.comuter aided designing is the importance part of operation management,it will increase the productivity of the business.Computer aided manufacturing is the important part of operation management.with the help of this computer aid manufacturing the machine will run by computers application software,after that application of computer aid application the production will increase.[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[9],[10],[8].

Economic Growth and Operation Management.

After the implementation of operation management principle we can face the challanges of globalization.Economy will develop when our good according to the standers.Quality control management is very important in this regard, quality control management maintain the stander of the goods.with the help of formula of quality control management we can establish the stander of quality.Project is the important part of operation management.with the quality control we can attain the stander of quality. Quality control provide the formula how to measure the quality control.Quality control provide the satisfaction of the customer.quality control is the index satisfaction of the customer can be maintained.Scheduleing is the important part of operation management.scheduleing in which maintain the resource according to the requirements and output and input,for example if one company have the order of units,in such cases schedule the resource according to the term and conditions.This is very beneficial for the operation management,in other words scheduleing provide the road map how to utilization of resources according to the needs and requirements.in the schedule the forward schedule is very important in operation management.schedule is key of success in manufacturing and business.[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[6],[7],[8],[9].

Famous models of operation management with the reference of economic growth.

Japan is the famous model of operation management. Because the good operation management, they achieved the highest growth of Development, Japan adopted the good supply chain management, because of this good supply chain management they came over all economics difficulties. In Japan the production management is very good because of good production management they utilized all the resources very good. Japan achieved the optimum level of utilization of resources. Japan adopted such models of material which is very use full for the production. In the recent years Japan achieved very rapid growth in the automobile industry. They achieved the highest record in the production in the automobile production. South Korea adopted the good operation management system. They adopted such method which increase the GDP.

Korea is best model of operation management.

In Korea the auto mobile sector is very developed and achieved the growth because of utilization of resources. In the recent years South Korea achieved the highest growth of economic growth and development. South Korea operation management model is the great symbol of other countries which are moving on the way of growth and development.

China is the big example of economic growth and development. They achieved the highest economic growth with the help of good operation management system. In China the utilization of resources very optimum level. Because of the good operation management they achieved the target of cost effectiveness. In this era of globalization China is the main hub of investment because of viable operation management. [1],[2],[3],[4],[6],[7],[8],[11]

Operation management Principles link with economic growth.

People, process, performance, project are the principles operation management, is very important for the economic growth and development. People is the first principle of operation management. Operation management guide how the people effectively work in the manufacturing sector. Operation management how the employee can be encouraged in the various stages. Operation management provide the guide how the good job is created for employees according to skills. Process is the important part of operation management. Process meaning how the output is converted in our put. Process meaning that better utilization of resources according to the needs. In the process system implantation of operation management system in the good and manufacturing sector. Performance is important part of operation management. With the help of performance it is analyzed that the goods are produced according to the needs and satisfaction of customer, and other words we can say it is maintained the quality standard according to the needs of customers. Project is the important part of the operation management, operation management is arrangement the activity completed in the specific time after the utilization of resources according to the needs. [1],[2],[3],[4],[6],[7],[8],[11]

Conclusion regarding principle of operation management. It is to be said that implementation of principle of operation management is essential for the economy, it can bring the growth and development in the economy. [1],[2],[3],[4],[6],[7],[8],[11]

Research regarding economics growth is possible with operation management

I conducted the qualitative and quantitative research

My hypothesis that Economics growth and development is possible with operation management.

Table.

Category. yes. No

Accountant	3.	0
MBA.	4	0
M.Com.	5.	0
Table 2:		
Cetogory	Yes.	No
Economist.	4.	0
Tax consultant	5.	0
Accountant.	6.	0

Majority of the audience that agree economics growth is possible with operation management.

Conclusion.

It to be concluded that the economics development is very important for society.if one country maintain the economics stability they can achieve the goal of economics growth and development.Economics provide the guideline how to run the economics effectively.Economics provide the guideline how the stability come in the country.Economics professional can better implemented the economics polices, there fore in various countries the economics subject are included in syallbus of Acedemics. There are the lots of connection between the economics with other subjects like financial management, Managerial economics, and international economics. Economics provide the path how to achieve the economics stability. Best implementation of economics polices can help the country to achieve the stable economics growth and development. The goal of economics growth and development can be achieved through the implement of operation management.with the help of better operation management the gross domestic product, as a result of operation management the country percapital and national income will increase.

The industrial growth can be possible with better operation management.with the help of operation management industrial growth and development can be improved in short time.Thus we can we can establish the relationshi between economic growth and operation management.

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